

summarized in Table 1. SB populations increased with level and duration of water in all environments (Table 2). Populations also

increased from pre-flood to maturity crop stages, irrespective of environment. □

Table 1. Incidence of SB in relation to different rice environments and different growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.

Rainfed rice environment	Variety	Year	SB incidence (%) at different growth stages				<i>r</i> for different growth stages ^a
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity	
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	1.5	4.5	4.5	6.5	+0.939
		1988	1.5	3.5	5.5	11.5	+0.956*
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	2.0	5.0	8.0	5.5	+0.708
		1988	2.5	5.5	9.5	25.5	+0.911
Very deepwater (above 1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	3.0	14.0	15.0	31.5	+0.950*
		1988	4.0	8.0	15.5	44.5	+0.981*
Flood (intermittent) (3 times up to 50 cm during 1987, 4 times up to 100 cm during 1988)	Madhukar	1987	9.5	14.5	16.5	25.0	+0.969*
		1988	-	-	-	-	-
<i>r</i> for different rice environments		1987	+0.937	+0.917	+0.848	+0.802	
		1988	+0.993	+0.862	+0.802	+0.772	

= significant at the 5% level.

Table 2. Stem damage due to SB at different rainfed rice environments and growth stages at Ghagharaghat, India, 1987-88.^a

Rainfed rice Environment	Variety	Year	Damaged stems (no.)			
			Preflood	Early elongation	Late elongation	Maturity
Shallow water (to 50 cm water)	Mahsuri	1987	3	9	9	13
		1988	3	7	11	23
Deepwater (50-100 cm)	Chakia 59	1987	4	10	16	11
		1988	5	11	19	51
Very deepwater (>1 m)	Jalmagna	1987	6	28	30	63
		1988	8	16	31	89
Flooded 2-3 times (to 50 cm) ^b	Madhukar	1987	19	29	33	50

^a200 stems selected diagonally in the field from each environment and at each growth stage. ^bThe 1988 crop failed because of flash flooding for more than 1 mo at crop initiation.

***Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. for biological control of rice hispa (RH) in Assam, India**

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During a routine search for an alternative to insecticides for control of RH *Dicladispa armigera* Olivier (Coleop-

tera, Chrysomelidae), we observed the majority of the test beetles reared in cages were dying of a fungal disease. In most cases, the beetles were found stuck to rice leaves and stems.

We cultured the fungus on potato dextrose agar medium incubated at ±24 °C. Fluffy growth of the fungus was noticed 3 d after inoculation on medium; it sporulated at 7 d. The spores were single-celled, hyaline, globose (0.8-), 1-3.5 µm in diameter, with clustering of conidiogenous rachis.

A hispa adult showing infestation with *Beauveria bassiana*. Magnification 11x.

The fungus was identified as *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuillemin; its pathogenicity was confirmed through Koch's postulates.

On RH adults, white frosty fungus growth emerged first through intersegmental membranes of the thorax and abdomen (see figure). Ultimately it covered the whole body and appendages. About 90% of the beetle population tested were killed. □

Arthropod diversity in tropical rice ecosystems

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Most organisms that live in ricefields are exogenous species that colonize the rice crop when cultivation begins. The recruitment phase is followed by an interaction phase, and the species present settle into a community.

A large proportion of the individual organisms are more or less trophically interlinked and unified in their dependence on rice.

Pest management actions are often directed at the community of rice arthropods rather than at individual